

The employee awareness of green human resource management practices and environmental cooperation in Bangladesh

Mst Kamrunnahar ¹, Akash Mahamud^{2*}, Jesmin Akter³, Md Uzzal Hossain⁴, Md. Abdur Rahaman⁵

¹Department of Arts in Bengali, National University Dhaka, Bangladesh

^{2*}Department of Public Administration, China University of geosciences, Wuhan

³Department of Applied Psychology, Southwest University, Chongqing, China

⁴Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, China University of geosciences, Wuhan, China

⁵Department of Public Administration, China University of geosciences, Wuhan, China

Abstract: Business communities have recently been increasing awareness of the significance of going green and adopting various environmental management techniques. As the corporate world is going global, the business is experiencing a shift from a conventional financial structure to a modern capacity-based economy ready to explore green economic facets of the company. Today, Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has become a key business strategy for significant organizations where Human Resource Departments play an active part in going green at the office. The principle of this study is to examine the extent of awareness of Green Human Resource Management among different levels of HR Managers from various organizations in Bangladesh. The findings of this study provide essential existing information on Green HRM though the practice of Green HRM in Bangladesh is insignificant. The results reveal that Green HRM knowledge depends on various factors. The study's practical implications identified the awareness level of Green HRM among Managers from different sectors in Bangladesh. Organizations should employ requisite Green HRM practices to achieve excellent organizational performance. Furthermore, the government may generate policies to endorse the above practices since, in the long term, accomplishing organizational excellence will reflect positively on the economy. All these may be facilitated through proactive corporate and national human resource development initiatives. The significance of the present study stems from the fact that very few studies have explored the awareness level of employees in the Green human resource management field in Bangladesh. The results provide insights into HRM practices in Bangladesh, an Indian subcontinent country. A region that has been neglected by management researchers and has therefore been less researched. Also, the insights gained from this study contribute to the future development of this line of research, particularly in a non-Western country like Bangladesh. Finally, the paper recommends some hypothetically fruitful HR initiatives for Green organizations.

Keywords: Green Human resource management, Awareness, Sustainable Environment, Strategic Human Resource Management.

*Corresponding Author: Akash Mahamud

Accepted: 18 January, 2023; **Published:** 31 January, 2023

How to cite this article: Mst Kamrunnahar, Akash Mahamud, Jesmin Akter, Md Uzzal Hossain, Md. Abdur Rahamana (2023). *The employee awareness of green human resource management practices and environmental cooperation in Bangladesh*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(1), 137-153. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595934>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Generating a sustainable workshop has been one of the critical issues around the world, specifically in western countries where people are more concerned with the workplace environment than emerging countries. However, awareness about the sustainable workplace has enlarged in emerging countries as some of the management of those countries have implemented their long-term development plans, including sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Omisore, Babarinde, Bakare, & Asekun-Olarinmoye, 2017; Osborn, Cutter, & Ullah, 2015; United Nations [UN], 2019). Bangladesh is one of those developing countries where sustainability has thrived alongside economic growth, as sustainability issues have been embedded in long-term plans, and the country has committed to transforming SDG awareness (2030 agenda). It has been encouraged by countrywide campaigns (UN, 2019). The country has already integrated the SDGs (proposed by UN Open Working Groups) into the national development agenda, and amongst the 17 goals of the SDGs, Goals 14, 16, and 17 are partially (18%) aligned with the Seventh Five Year Plan of Bangladesh's government.

In contrast, the rest of the 14 goals are thematically fully aligned (United Nations Development Programme, 2018). From these perspectives, it is clear that the government of Bangladesh is serious about ensuring sustainability in its functional and infrastructural movements and developments.

The term "green human resource management" is currently the most common and popular thing. Green is all about HRM-related Practices essential to achieve the environmental objectives of Companies to oblige to sustainable development (Apriyanti, 2020). CSR is a critical issue in introducing green human resource management. Particularly environmental management has nowadays become a global social norm. Bangladesh's most significant developing sector is the Garments industry, which is currently a major environmental polluter. The GHRM assistances to prevent that kind of problem. Human Resource Management conducts environmental management is called green Human Resource Management (Gazi, 2020). The perception of GHRM originated from the impetus for organizations to integrate sustainability into their internal activities and decision-making. The perception of sustainable development first entered common usage when outlined in the United Nations Brundtland Report, which defined it as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." Sustainable development differs from traditional approaches to growth by integrating economic development, social inclusion, and environmental protection considerations. Greening is a holistic process aimed at more innovative energy usage, low costs, and low wastage using sustainable resources or recyclable materials for products, targets, etc., which are environmentally friendly. Studies have indicated that going green is economically valuable, directly impacts the business's bottom-line profits, and enhances investment return (Jafri, 2012).

The twenty-first century has been presentation delicate awareness in environmental concerns all around the world, irrespective of interrelated fields, be it politics, public, or business. The recent global interest in environmental [1]mentalism has arisen from specific treaties to combat climate change, e.g., Kyoto 1997, Bali 2007, and Copenhagen 2009 (Victor, 2001). Owing to the harmful consequences of industrial pollution and waste materials, including toxic chemicals, governments and NGOs around the globe promoted regulations and policies with the effect of slowing down and, to some extent, even reversing the destruction of natural resources and its negative effect on the mankind and the society as a whole (Christmann & Taylor, 2002; Shrivastava & Berger, 2010).

Human Resource Management (HRM) is an essential function of management that deals with an organization's most valuable asset, human resources. The total framework of HRM is presently being considered in the light of sustainability entirely over. Escalating the statement, I struggle that Green Human Resource Management is the maximum significant element of sustainability. In this paper, we exclusively focus on Green Human Resource Management (GHRM), where Human Resource Management (HRM) is engaged in managing the environment within an organization. Mampara (2013) defines Green HRM as the use of HRM policies to encourage the sustainable use of resources within business initiatives and promote the cause of environmentalism, which further boosts employee morale and satisfaction. Others describe Green HRM as using HRM policies, philosophies, and practices to promote sustainable use of business resources and thwart any ward harm arising from environmental concerns in organizations (Zoogah, 2011). Green enterprises within HRM form portion of more comprehensive corporate social responsibility programs. Green HR consists of two significant elements: environment-friendly HR practices and the preservation of knowledge capital (Mandip, 2012). Within an organization, human resources and their systems are the basic foundation of any business, whether financial or sustainable. They are responsible for planning and executing those eco-friendly policies to create a green atmosphere. Going green would be easier to crack by facilitating human resources and implementing sustainable policies. Though a substantial extent of existing literature deals with Green HRM, there still needs to be cleared associated with implementing green HR management policies in organizations around the globe to attain absolute green corporate culture. This article comprehends how corporations are taking initiatives to endorse environment management programs by developing human resource policies and ascertaining different processes involved in green HRM based on extant literature. Further, we review the literature on the HR aspects of GHRM, which helps identify how corporations today develop human resource policies for going green. The study also provides simplified insight into some standard GHRM processes and attempts to suggest some green initiatives for HR.

Objectives

The primary purpose of this study is to:

- ✓ Afford a basic understanding of green HRM to the readers,
- ✓ Highlight different significant works on green HRM by supplementary workers, and
- ✓ Elaborate on various green practices that can be incorporated for building a Green workplace.
- ✓ Efforts to suggest some green initiatives for HR.

Methodology

The study is mainly founded on secondary data. Existent literature related to the topic was collected from different databases, websites, and other available sources. A methodical review of the collected literature was done in aspect.

Green human resource management (GHRM)

It means using green practices and progressions in the green HR professionals. It includes finding human capital, accepting, formulating, implementing, and rewarding management. These goals will target the overall impression of the organization. The elements of human resource management are usually measured traditionally and practice multiple greens approaches in all conducts.

The term Green HRM has become the buzzword within the business field, and its significance has increased manifold over time. This term has also closed position as a hot topic in recent research works since the awareness of environmental management and sustainable development has been increasingly rising day by day all around the globe. Green HRM includes awareness of environmental affairs and stands for the social and economic well-being of both the organization and the employees within a broader prospect.

Before proceeding further, first of all, we take up the question, "what is Green HRM?" Different authors have given different definitions for this term, such as—"Green HRM is the use of HRM policies to promote the sustainable

use of resources within organizations and, more generally, promotes the causes of environment sustainability" (Marhatta & Adhikari, 2013, p. 2). GHRM is directly responsible for creating a green workforce that understands, appreciates, and practices green initiatives and maintains its green objectives throughout the HRM process of recruiting, hiring, training, compensating, developing, and advancing the firm's human capital (Mathapati, 2013, p. 2). It refers to the policies, practices, and systems that make employees of the organization green for the benefit of the individual, society, the natural environment, and the business (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014, p. 104).

GHRM is accountable for generating a green employee that understands, appreciates, and performs green initiatives. It maintains its green objectives throughout the HRM process of recruiting, hiring, training, compensating, developing, and advancing the firms' human capital (Mathapati, 2013). It refers to the policies, practices, and systems that make employees of the organization green for the benefit of the individual, society, the natural environment, and the business (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014). Green HRM involves two essential elements: environment-friendly HRM practices and the preservation of knowledge capital (Jain, 2009). Green HRM also involves reducing carbon footprint via less paper printing, video conferencing, interviews, etc.

Figure: Four Meaning of green or greening in the context of HRM

Source: Opatha,H.H.& Arulrajah, A.A.(2014)

Who is green employee?

The employee who is a natural lover, eco-activist, non-polluter, and conservationist of resources of the organization?

I can recognize the green employee in the organization. The following questions should be enquired:

- ✓ Does he switch off his computer when he finishes work?
- ✓ Does he use a mug rather than disposable cups?
- ✓ Does he print out his emails on both sides of the paper?
- ✓ Does he use public transport or walk/cycle to work?
- ✓ Does he recycle any garbage/rubbish he creates at work?
- ✓ If he is the last to leave, does he ensure all unnecessary lights and equipment are switched off?

The study of the rationale

Green HRM initiatives help companies find substitute ways to cut costs without losing their top talent and endorse sustainable business practices. It may assistance employers in building brand image and reputation. Green HRM will make employees and society members aware of using natural resources more economically and encourage eco-friendly products. It also emphasizes long-term employment security to avoid disruption for employees, their families, and communities. Increasing employee awareness of Green HRM is stipulated for the modern competitive business world.

Theoretical framework

Employee awareness of green HRM depends on various factors. The following framework has been developed based on the literature study and experts' opinions.

Fig: Factors to increase employee awareness on Green HRM

Ghrm functions imminent direction

GHRM is a platform that supports generate a green employee that can understand and appreciate green culture in an organization. Such green initiatives can maintain its objectives throughout the HRM process of recruiting, hiring and training, compensating, developing, and advancing the firm's human capital (Dutta, 2012). A company's Human Resource Department can significantly create a sustainability culture (Harmon et al., 2010). HR processes play an essential role in translating Green HR policy into practice (Renwick, 2008); therefore, human capital and its management are instrumental to fulfilling EM objectives (Hersey, 1998). Huslid (1995) mentions the selection processes, incentive compensation, performance management systems, employee involvement, and training to be central to the company's success. Consequently, the argument is advanced that the HR function is instrumental in realizing organizational change aimed at acclimatizing to the new-found requirements for corporations and, therefore, also a potentially significant contributor to such a strategic issue.

It must be acknowledged that the intersection of sustainability, the natural environment, and HR management are new areas in fast development and, therefore, not characterized by a fully developed body of writings (Jackson et al., 2011). Ulrich, Brockbank, and Johnson (2009) point out that many HR systems need to be aligned with each other in

order to increase the likelihood that the organization will achieve its strategy. In their study, Cherian and Jacob (2012) identified that recruitment, training, employee motivation, and rewards are essential human dimensions that contribute to improving employee implementation of green management principles. In order to make sure that the organization gets the right employee green inputs and the right employee green performance on the job, it is indispensable that HRM functions are adapted or modified to be green (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014, p. 107). In this part of the paper, we briefly describe a few specific functional HRM activities which identity with the sustainability and the natural environment at the workplace and also provide opportunities for research in future.

Green recruitment

Green Human Resource Management is a relatively new agenda in management and HRM literature. Green HRM practices include using the lowest number of papers for all HR functions daily, like recruitment and selection, training, performance review and more, to create a sustainable and environment-friendly workplace. The two essential elements of Green HR are environment-friendly HR practices and the preservation of knowledge capital.

Bangladeshi firms should adopt green HRM practices to preserve the natural environment, ensure a healthy working environment, gain a competitive advantage by ensuring corporate social responsibility, and reduce intervention from the government. Furthermore, other law enforcement agencies develop eco-friendliness and environmental learning among employees, maximize the use of resources, save costs and strengthen the company image. With proper understanding and implementation of green HR practices, any firm can sustainably improve its social and organizational performance.

Attracting high-quality staff is a critical HR challenge in the "war for talent" (Renwick et al., 2013, p. 2). Holtom, Mitchell, Lee, and Eberly (2008), in their study on turnover and retention of employees, argue that the most critical benefit dimensions of HR and sustainability are retention/recruitment and satisfaction. Firms are now beginning to recognize that gaining a reputation as a green employer is an effective way to attract new talent (Phillips, 2007; Stringer, 2009). German organizations such as Siemens, BASF, Bayer and Mannesmann custom environmental activities and a green image to attract high-quality staff. The Rover Group carmaker in Britain makes environmental responsibilities and qualifications portion of every job profile (Wehrmeyer, 1996, p. 30). Increasingly, green job descriptions with environmental aspects are now included for employees within the recruitment agenda. Green recruitment can be distinct as the procedure of acquisition individuals with knowledge, skills, approaches, and behaviors that categorize with environmental management systems within an organization. According to Wehrmeyer (1996), recruitment practices can support effective environmental management by ensuring that new entrants are familiar with an organization's environmental culture and can maintain its environmental values.

Green recruiting is a system where the focus is given to the importance of the environment and making it a significant element within the organization. Complementing is the recruits are also enthusiastic and, to some extent, passionate about working for an environmentally friendly "green" company. Recruiting candidates with a green bend of mind makes it easy for firms to induct professionals aware of sustainable processes. Furthermore, they are already familiar with basics like recycling, conservation, and creating a more logical world (Grolleau et al., 2012); in their study on the impact of the environmental standards of a company on the recruitment of an employee, they found that the environmental commitment of the company adds to the profile of a company. In their primary survey, they found that professionals were more concerned about a company's environmental strategy.

Sustainable environment collaboration in green hrm for Bangladesh

Green HRM performs human resource management practices to inspire the sustainable use of resources within business organizations and, more specifically, signifies environmental Sustainability. The reason for going green is to use products, processes and methods that would not adversely impact the environment through pollution or wastage of natural resources. Green HRM involves environmentally-friendly human resource policies and practices to help

organizations achieve their monetary goal. Through environmental branding, protect the environment from any negative impacts that might be caused by the policies & actions adopted by the organizations. Environmental Sustainability is often defined as the "ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. In environmental protectionism, the concept of green management for sustainable development imparts various meanings, all of which ultimately aim to balance industrial growth for wealth creation and to protect the natural environment so that future generations might not suffer. Green HRM is a paradigm shift from the previous HRM practices, which emphasizes the right people at the right job. Green HRM is the set of activities (recruitment, training and development, performance and appraisal, employee relations, pay and reward) that manage an organization's human resources intending to achieve organizational goals through ensuring environmental Sustainability. The process sets in motion with the recruitment of prospective green employees into the organization, followed by green training and development and green performance management.

Moreover, appraisal, environment-friendly employee-employer relationships focus on employee involvement, and green performance-based pay and rewards. Moreover, end with conducting exit interviews with those leaving the organization voluntarily or involuntarily and using the survey results to improve the employee management systems. A vital part of green human resource management is achieving organizational financial goals through environmental Sustainability (policies and actions focused on minimal or no environmental damage). Recruits must be stimulated to ensure they understand and brutally approach their corporate environmental culture; therefore, sustainable development issues must be integrated into the recruitment process. Employee training and development programs should include social and environmental issues at all levels, from technical health and safety considerations on the shop floor to strategic sustainability issues at the executive management and board level. Green orientation programs for fresh employees should be an integral part of the training and development process.

Using performance management in environmental management presents the challenges of measuring environmental performance standards across different units of the organization and acquiring important data on the environmental performance of managers. Companies like Tata Group have inaugurated corporate-wide environmental performance standards to measure environmental performance standards and developed green information systems and audits (to acquire important data on managerial environmental performance). One way performance management systems can be successfully kicked off in an organization is by strapping the performance evaluations to the job descriptions revealing the specific green goals and tasks. For example, performance appraisal can swathe topics such as environmental incidents, usage of environmental responsibilities, reducing carbon emissions, and communicating environmental concerns and policies. The core goals of green human resource management are sorted with managing people and relationships between employers and employees. Consequently, it deals with the use of labour productivity to accomplish strategic business objectives of the organization and congregates the needs of individual workers. In business activities, the human factor is crucial in addition to physical factors and capital. Employees and human resources, in general, are the leading factor determining the success or failure of any business organization like a commercial bank. Organizations consider the HR department to play a major role in staffing, training and helping to manage people so that people and the organization are performing at maximum capability in a highly fulfilling manner. Green HRM is increasingly considered a contemporary development in the global business to reshape employment relationships as a tool that may have effectively substituted other management. It is the time for Sustainability which could be achieved through Green HRM. As HRM has tools of a system which attracts, develops, motivates, and retains people, the scope of HRM is extensive. Researches in behavioral sciences illustrate that new trends in managing workers and advances in the field of training have expanded the scope of the HR function in recent years and should be more environments friendly. The use of employee participation in environmental management has been noted to help prevent pollution in workplaces. Many prominent Gurus of HRM stated that the environmental involvement approach in environmental management motivates the workers and allows them to detect problems like leakages in the

production process. Environmental initiatives should be integrated into the compensation system by offering employees a benefits package that rewards employees for green performance. Monetary-based environmental reward systems have developed an important proportion of monthly executive bonuses in developed countries, which depend on environmental management performance outcomes. In the U.S., companies such as Du Pont base their administrative compensation and bonus system for middle managers and senior officers in fragment on environmental stewardship practices. where bonuses can be over 10 per cent if they develop an environmentally gentle pesticide for agriculture or a non-polluting. Exit means voluntarily or involuntarily leaving the organization. As the last task of the green HRM process, the HR manager will conduct exit interviews for those leaving. The results of the exit interview, if the exit is environmentally related, need to be improved.

Moreover, arrangements for outplacement counselling shall be made for those fired for bad environmental performance. In this context, the goal of outplacement counselling is to provide the leaving employees with a knowledge base, particularly about the environment, so they might be able to find a job elsewhere. If the HRM department follows Green HRM practices, it could be more environmentally friendly and sustainable in the long run. The banking industry is the thrust sector of Bangladesh. At present, 39 private commercial banks, four govt. banks, ten foreign banks and nine specialized banks are providing their services. A large segment of people is employed here. As for this, the Green Human Resource Management Practices will play a crucial role in creating benchmarking practices regarding human resource management. This contemporary issue of Green HRM is generally indefinite to these banks. Bangladesh Bank has already been issued green banking guidelines, which are to be followed by every bank. Nevertheless, Green HRM is a new concept in the banking sector. Banks are service-oriented organizations. Human resources are the main engine of banks, so if Green HRM practice is introduced, it will surely affect the performance of these banks. Green Human Resources Management has emerged from companies engaging in practices interrelated to protective the environment and sustaining ecological stability. Green HRM can performance a valuable role in business in endorsing environment-related issues by espousing and following Green HR policies and actions. Green HRM can develop corporate image and brand. Green HRM department will play an important role in making the employees aware of and concerned for preserving natural resources and contributing to pollution control, waste management and manufacture of eco-friendly products.

Green performance management

Performance management (PM) is how employees are encouraged to develop their professional skills to help achieve organizational goals and objectives. The recognition of the corporate strategy culminates in the PM. Through the EM affecting international business strategy, PM is also being predisposed by the green trend in a conceivable constructive manner. Green performance management involves of issues interrelated to environmental concerns and strategies of the company. Similarly concentrates on the usage of environmental responsibilities. Epstein and Roy (1997) concluded that when HR managers integrate environmental performance into PM systems, they safeguard environment management against any damage. Today some firms deal with the issue of PM by installing corporate-wide environmental performance standards and Green information systems/audits to gain valuable data on environmental performance (Marcus & Fremeth, 2009).

The maximum critical feature of PM is performance appraisal. In addition to meeting the criteria of reliability, validity, and fairness, effective performance appraisals provide helpful feedback to employees and support continuous improvements in the firm's environmental outcomes (Jackson et al., 2011, p. 7). Environmental PA issues concern managers' need to be held accountable for EM performance and broader performance objectives (Renwick et al., 2013, p. 5). Future research on green performance appraisal should focus on issues such as environmental incidents, environmental responsibilities, communication of environmental policy, and green information system and audits. The job explanation should be affiliated with green tasks and goals to be accomplished. The HR staff should modify the performance appraisal rating system to include dimensions for rating people on behavioral and technical competencies:

teamwork, collaboration, diversity, innovation, and environmental stewardship. Such competencies would emphasize the company's essential values (Liebowitz, 2010, p. 53). Managers should discuss the performance of the employees and give the needed feedback during the scheduled time of appraisal and all year round. This practice will assist the employees to augment their knowledge, skills and capability.

Green training and expansion

Training and development are a practice that focuses on developing employees' skills, knowledge, and attitudes, preventing the deterioration of EM-related knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Zoogah, 2011, p. 17). Green training and development educate employees about the value of EM, train them in working methods that conserve energy, reduce waste, diffuse environmental awareness within the organization, and provide an opportunity to engage employees in environmental problem-solving (Zoogah, 2011). Green T&D activities make employees aware of different aspects and values of environment management. It helps them embrace different conservation methods, including waste management within an organization. Further, it improves the skill of an employee to deal with different environmental matters. Ramus (2002), in a survey of managers on best management practices, concluded that environmental training and education, along with establishing a favorable environmental culture for the employees. Where they feel that they are part of environmental outcomes were the most important HRM processes that facilitate achieving environmental goals. The role of HR in achieving a sustainable culture suggests that the HR Department can offer leadership development workshops to help managers develop their "front wheel" soft, people skills, or behavioral competencies in teamwork, diversity, managing change, and collaboration (Liebowitz, 2010, p.3). Future research that facilitates green training on the one hand and helps organizations on the other to develop eco-friendly managers who, without any hesitation, can indulge as well as promote sustainability throughout the process would be instrumental.

Concluding the above discussion, we envisage that the need of the hour is: that organizations should train their employees on best business practices enthused with green initiatives. Besides, sustainable training and education employees should also be adept at educating the customers regarding the advantages of becoming more earth-friendly and buying green products.

Green compensation

Rewards and recompense are the major HRM procedures concluded which employees are rewarded for their performance. These HR practices are the most powerful method linking an individual's interest to that of the organization. We also assert that incentives and rewards can influence employees' attention to the maximum at work and motivate them to exert maximum effort to achieve organizational goals.

In the context of Green HRM, rewards and compensation are potential tools for supporting environmental activities in organizations. Following a strategic approach to reward and management, modern organizations are developing reward systems to encourage eco-friendly initiatives embarked upon by their employees. The statement is supported by a survey conducted in the UK by CIPD/KPMG that estimated that 8% of UK firms were rewarding green behaviors with various types of awards and financial incentives (Phillips, 2007, p. 9). In a similar study by Forman and Jorgensen (2001) on the importance of employee participation in environmental programs, it was observed that employee commitment to environmental management programs was increased when they were offered compensation to take up duties concerning environmental responsibility. The efficacy of green rewards and compensation was best observed in a study by Berrone and Gomez-Mejia (2009) on 469 US firms operating in high-polluting industries.

They found that firms with eco-friendly performance paid their CEOs more than non-eco-friendly firms. They also concluded that long-term company results in accordance to pay were associated with tremendous pollution prevention success. Literature review exposes that incentives encourage executives to usage accounting and additional works to achieve short-term results and augment themselves (Benz & Frey, 2007; Denis, Hanouna, & Sarin, 2006).

Green employee relations

The relationship facilitates motivation and morale of the employees as well as increases productivity. Employee relations involve employee participation and empowerment activities. It also helps prevent and resolve problems arising at the workplace that may affect the work. Positive employee relations are an intangible and enduring asset and a source of competitive advantage for any organization.

Employee participation in Green initiatives increases the chances of better green management by aligning employees' goals, capabilities, motivations, and perceptions with green management practices and systems. Involving employees in EM has been reported to improve EM systems such as efficient resource usage (Florida & Davison, 2001); reducing waste (May & Flannery, 1995); and reducing pollution from workplaces (Kitazawa & Sarkis, 2000). Several workers in their study concluded that individual empowerment positively influences productivity and performance and facilitates self-control, individual thinking, and problem-solving skills (Renwick, 2008; Wee & Quazi, 2005).

An important way in which employee involvement and participation can be encouraged within the organization is to pursue entrepreneurs within the company who are socially or ecologically concerned with, known as eco-entrepreneurs (Mandip, 2012, p. 246). Eco-friendly ideas should be welcomed by all employees irrespective of their designation, which will encourage their interest in environmental issues and make the best use of applying their skills. The HR staff needs to pressure the management to create participative work in an environment where the employees are free to put up their ideas on green issues. They are the ones who, in reality, are responsible for implementing ethical corporate behaviour in the organization's day-to-day life. That means the achievement of green outcomes will largely depend on employees' willingness to collaborate (Collier & Esteban, 2007). Frequently, the best concepts come from the employees who work in that area (Casler, Gundlach, Persons, & Zivnuska, 2010).

The scope of employee relations should be broadened by initiating a suggestion scheme within the organization, wherein each employee from the topmost to the lowest level gets an opportunity to contribute to the scheme. This practice will help create greater awareness of green issues; new ideas for eco-friendly practices may crop up from different sources. IBM UK has an action-team program. It gives grants to encourage employees and their families to get involved in a local environmental project (Wehrmeyer, 1996, p. 31).

Other benefits of employee involvement are improvement in employee and organizational health and safety and the development of eco-friendly staff. Keeping the policies to the long-term trust among the management and employees will be built, allowing employees to express their ideas at the workplace and help create a climate conducive to green management practices and systems.

Key challenges of green human resource management

Human resources assume the vital task of supervising the work of employees from entrance to resignation. Presently, the company is devoted to green business; consequently, the human resources office is responsible for practicing environmental awareness and human resources systems. The human resource approach is developing rules on how to monitor individuals. They describe how the organization handles theories and estimates of individuals. The human resources strategy provides a summary direction for managing human resources. Deshwal (2015) pointed out the difficulties associated with green human resource management.

- ✓ It is challenging to change workers' behavior within a limited time frame.
- ✓ Not every employee is equally persuaded to be interested in developing green human resource management practices in the organization.
- ✓ Creating a green human resource management lifestyle throughout the organization is an awkward and lengthy process.
- ✓ It requires high speculation at the bottom stage and a near-medium rate of return.
- ✓ Purchasing and recruiting green employees with quality gifts is a difficult task.

- ✓ It isn't easy to evaluate the feasibility of green human resource management practices in the behavior of employees.
- ✓ The problem that human resources experts face is that they must rely on them to provide basic green structures, green procedures, green tools, and green reasoning to make the best choice and establish the organization's future green pioneers.

Implications of the study

The study findings give elasticity HR specialists a more thoughtful comprehension of achieving predominant green innovativeness among their employees. Primarily when firms want to transform the complications brought by environmental issues into circumstances, it should be understood that knocking resources into ecological matters was not an exercise in futility, endeavors, or resources, which lengthened the weight of a firm. Interestingly, it has become a feasible method to deal with accumulation upper hands by refining green innovativeness these days, which can help firms catch new green markets. Consequently, organizations should appropriately build awareness of environmental management and exertion to set up an environmentally inviting portrait to pull in correspondingly invested job searchers. To animate employees' green energy and innovativeness, firms should make a functioning help environment, for example, giving budgetary help, presenting progressed environmental management strategies, and building up a framework that energizes workers' green imagination. Second, organizations need to adjust the idea of green into their long-run environmental techniques, which would require a high level of green human resources management, including green preparation and advancement, green pay, compensates, etc. The environmental procedure gives a bearing to organizations to develop green intensity. It makes an environment-friendly climate, which gives the vital resources and backing to create thoughts that are helpful for the manageable advancement of the organization. Along these lines, the hr office should genuinely execute green human resources management practices. For instance, while selecting new employees, give more consideration to workers' environmental quality and environmental consciousness. Green training should not just concentrate on improving workers' environmental security aptitudes; they should likewise endeavor to pass on the organization's environmental management objectives and qualities to the people. Third, this investigation gives critical recommendations to chiefs utilizing transformational initiatives to manage Green Human Resources Management and motivate workers' green enthusiasm. Pioneers can use transformational practices in the beginning periods of Green Human Resources Management advancement to set up standards for collaboration, green, and development. They can submit a specific measure of organizational resources to devise eco-friendly enthusiasm and inventiveness for workers. In this way, transformational administration can improve firms' the green imagination by impacting Green Human Resources Management and invigorating workers' innovativeness.

To remind specialists that to improve green imagination and add green aggressiveness, firms can concentrate on encouraging transformational administration, causing chiefs to assume a crucial job. Some administrative mediations may be significant decisions, such as green group building, conceptualizing rivalries, or payment plans for expanding green innovativeness. At last, as we are aware, China is the second biggest economy on the planet. Until the mid-21st century, undertakings have been exorbitantly seeking financial advantages and ignoring environmental issues during the time spent on advancement. With the debasement of the environment, the attention to us relating environmental insurance has steadily expanded. For example, The Chinese government is additionally effectively advancing the change of the advancement model of ventures and encouraging undertakings to respect financial improvement and security of the biological environment as similarly significant, which may convey specific difficulties to the organizations. Through environmental management, assembling the ecological energy of workers, and upgrading their green inventiveness; in any case, it is likewise feasible for organizations to transform difficulties into circumstances and increase an upper hand. For organizations that may face similar promotions in emerging economies,

our inspection can prove that their organizations have changed their financial improvement models and achieved green promotion goals. In addition, past studies have emerged as a helpful link between the environment, human resource management, and the company. The organization has multiple purposes, and it can accept green human resource management practices. These practices will neither bring benefits to the organization but also provide an essential resource or part of the organization that is ignored (i.e., employees) Point of contact. Green human resource management practices improve the spirit of employees, which may save the environment, which will be valuable to both the organization and the workers.

Conclusion

It is not a hidden fact that human resource is the most important asset of an organization that plays an important role in managing the employees. At the moment, the current improved trend of corporate emphasis on greening the business, the contemporary HR managers have been dispensed with additional responsibility of incorporating the Green HR philosophy in corporate mission statement along with HR policies. Variations in corporate perceptions interrelated to the environmental initiatives can be realized in written policy statements, environmental job designations, marketing strategies, capital investments, auditing practices, new product design and development, and production processes (Molina-Azorín, Claver-Cortés, Pereira-Moliner, & Tarí, 2009; Sharfman & Fernando, 2008). Green procedure and strategies are now making their system through within the HR space complementing the prevailing green practices and initiatives. Green HR efforts have resulted in augmented efficiencies, cost reduction, employee retention, and enhanced productivity, besides other tangible benefits.

Though the green movement and Green HR are still in the stages of infancy, growing awareness within organizations of the significance of green issues have compelled them to embrace environment- friendly HR practices with a specific focus on waste management, recycling, reducing the carbon footprint, and using and producing green products. Clearly, a majority of the employees feel strongly about the environment and, exhibit greater commitment and job satisfaction toward an organization that is ever ready to go "Green." The effects of GHRM practices are multifaceted and require constant monitoring to recognize their potential impact on HRM issues. The Greening HRM involves specific HR's policies and practices aligned with the three sustainability pillars—environment, social, and economic balance (Yusliza, Ramayah, & Othman, 2015, p. 1) The responsibility of the present generations, HR managers are to create awareness among the youngsters and among the people working for the organization about the Green HRM, Green movement, utilization of natural resources and helping the corporate to maintain proper environment, and retain the natural resources for our future generation i.e. sustainable development(Mathapati, 2013, p. 2).

The future of Green HRM appears promising for all the stakeholders of HRM, be it the employers, employees, practitioners, or academicians. We propose that GHRM has substantial scope for research in management field but lacks behind in practice within academic arena; hence, there is a need to bridge the gap between professional GHRM practices and preaches in research and teaching environmental management. Pushing further, we look forward to see more research on this topic in near future, which can highlight the role of HRM activities in supporting green initiatives and to some extent even influencing environmental management strategies. Studies that observe the overall impact of GHRM systems rather than individual practices would be particularly helpful in this respect.

Such studies can help organizations to reduce degradation of the environment become healthier both physically and financially and, make the world a cleaner and safer place to live. On the concluding note, we would like to add that HR is the major role player in implementing GHRM practices and policies. Apart from this, they have a crucial role to play in recruitment of new employees who are more responsible toward green business practices thus, indirectly saving the Earth. Last, but not the least, HR has significant opportunity to contribute to the organization's green movement and plays important role in enthusing, facilitating, and motivating employees for taking up green practices for greener business.

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Akash Mahamud

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Akash Mahamud is a scholar of China University of geosciences, Wuhan, China. He awarded his Master's degree from China University of geosciences, Wuhan, China. In Bangladesh, he was an expert in pharmaceuticals (Supply Chain Management) field. Currently, he is researching in **“The effectiveness on environmental policy to reduce CO2 emissions in Bangladesh.** He has research interest in FDI, Trade (export & import), economic development and environment economics, CO2 emissions and Public Management. However, many studies supported negative and positive effects for both cases.

